

ON A LIMIT OF A SEQUENCE OF THE NUMERICAL FUNCTION

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In this paper is studied the limit of the following sequence:

$$T(n) = 1 - \log \sigma_S(n) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_S(p_i^k)}$$

We shall demonstrate that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T(n) = -\infty$.

We shall consider define the sequence $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, \dots, p_n$ = the n th prime number and the function $\sigma_S: \mathbf{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbf{N}$, $\sigma_S(x) = \sum_{\substack{d|x \\ d>0}} S(d)$, where S is Smarandache Function.

For example: $\sigma_S(18) = S(1) + S(2) + S(3) + S(6) + S(9) + S(18) = 0 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 6 = 20$

We consider the natural number p_m^n , where p_m is a prime number. It is known that $(p-1)r + 1 \leq S(p^r) \leq pr$ so $S(p^r) > (p-1)r$.

Next, we can write $\sigma_S(p^r) = \sum_{s=0}^r S(p^s) > \sum_{s=0}^r (p-1)s = (p-1) \frac{r(r+1)}{2}$

$$\sigma_S(p_i^k) > (p_i - 1) \frac{k(k+1)}{2}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_S(p_i^k)} < \frac{2}{(p_i - 1)k(k+1)}$$

This involves that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_S(p_i^k)} < \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{2}{(p_i - 1)k(k+1)} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{p_i - 1} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{2}{k(k+1)} \right)$$

$\sigma_S(k) > 0, \quad \forall k \geq 2$ and $p_a^b \leq p_m^n$ if $a \leq m$ and $b \leq n$ and $p_a^b = p_c^d$ if $a = c$ and $b = d$.

But $\sigma_S(p_m^n) > (p_m - 1) \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ implies that $-\log \sigma_S(p_m^n) < -\log(p_m - 1) \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$
because $\log x$ is strictly increasing from 2 to $+\infty$.

Next, using inequality (1) we obtain

$$T(p_m^n) = 1 - \log \sigma_S(p_m^n) + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_S(p_i^k)} < 1 - \log(p_m - 1) \frac{n(n+1)}{2} +$$

$$+ \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k - 1} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{2}{k(k+1)} \right)$$

But $\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{2}{k(k+1)} = \frac{2p_m}{p_m+1} \Rightarrow T(p_m^{p_m}) < 1 + \log 2 - 2 \log p_m - \log(p_m - 1) +$

$$+ \frac{2p_m}{p_m+1} \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k - 1}$$

$$T(p_m^{p_m}) < 1 + \log 2 + 2 \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) + \frac{2p_m}{p_m+1} \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k - 1} - 2 \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} - \log(p_m - 1)$$

We have $\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k - 1} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k}$.

So: $T(p_m^{p_m}) < 1 + \log 2 + 2 \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{p_m}{p_m+1} - 1 \right) - \log(p_m - 1)$

And then $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} T(p_m^{p_m}) \leq 1 + \log 2 + 2 \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) - \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left[2 \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \frac{1}{p_m+1} \right] -$

$$- \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \log(p_m - 1) = 1 + \log 2 + 2 \lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) - \lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{2}{p_m+1} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \right] -$$

$$- \lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \log(p_m - 1) = 1 + \log 2 + 2\gamma - 0 - \infty = -\infty.$$

It is known that $\lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) = \gamma$ (Euler's constant) and

$$\lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2}{p_m+1} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) = 0.$$

In conclusion $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T(n) = -\infty$.

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